

PREDICTIONS OF CRACK GROWTH RATES, R-RATIO EFFECTS AND OVERLOAD BEHAVIOUR BASED ON SMOOTH SPECIMEN LCF TEST DATA AND USING A STRIP YIELD-TYPE MODEL

S. J. Williams¹, M. T. Whittaker¹ & M. C. Hardy²

Plastic 2D plane stress analyses have been run on a finite element (FE) model containing a sharp semi-circular notch representing an edge crack. Stress-distance profiles ahead of the crack tip (notch root) were extracted at the maximum and minimum points of a range of fatigue cycles with different loading amplitudes. These were used with data from smooth specimen Low Cycle Fatigue (LCF) tests to predict the build-up of fatigue damage at regularly-spaced locations ahead of the crack tip as it moves towards them. Knowledge of the number of fatigue cycles required to fail the material at successive calculation locations then allows crack growth rates to be calculated at the corresponding crack lengths. FE analyses were performed for a wide range of K_{max} values at loading R-ratios of 0, -1 and 0.5, and the growth rate predictions were compared with test data. The method was then extended to predict how the crack growth rates recover after a change in the applied load. The material studied was the nickel-based superalloy fine grain (FG) RR1000 at 20°C.

Keywords: crack growth, finite element analysis, low cycle fatigue, R-ratio effects

INTRODUCTION

As part of a wider programme to investigate crack growth phenomena such as closure, R-ratio (min/max load) effects, overload retardation and high temperature tunnelling, non-linear finite element (FE) analyses using the ABAQUS code have been run on a range of 2D and 3D models containing sharp notches representing cracks. This paper takes the predicted maximum and minimum plastic stress fields from 2D plane stress analyses on geometry representing an edge crack together with data from smooth specimen Low Cycle Fatigue (LCF) tests to predict the build-up of fatigue damage at evenly spaced locations ahead of the crack tip (notch root) as it moves towards them. When the fatigue damage at a location reaches unity the material there is considered to have failed and hence the crack has reached that position. Knowing the number of fatigue cycles required to fail the material at successive calculation locations then allows crack growth rates to be calculated. The material studied was the nickel-based superalloy fine grain (FG) RR1000 at 20°C.

Similar fatigue-based crack growth methods, also known as Critical Damage Models, have been published by Noroozi et al. [1] and Ferreira et al. [2]. The basis of Noroozi's model is shown in Figure 1 below, taken from [1]. As with the work described in this paper, the crack tip is represented as a sharp semi-circular notch. The notch radius is ρ^* , and the fatigue damage is assessed using averaged loading conditions in material strips of this width ahead of the notch. The Creager-Paris [3] solution is used to determine the mean tensile elastic stresses in each strip ahead of the crack tip, and the compressive elastic stress fields are determined by treating the crack tip as a circular hole. The Neuber [4] construction and a Ramberg-Osgood [5] stress-strain curve are then used to calculate the plastic Smith-Watson-Topper [6] parameter and hence fatigue damage and crack growth rates.

¹Institute of Structural Materials, Swansea University, Fabian Way, Swansea SA1 8EN, United Kingdom

²Rolls-Royce plc, PO Box 31, Moor Lane, Derby DE22 8BJ, United Kingdom

The dimension ρ^* is used as a fitting parameter to line the predictions up with the material's threshold stress intensity value, which is required as an input to the model. Reasonable predictions of crack growth behaviour were made for a wide range of loading R-ratios, but it was considered that the use of plastic finite element analyses to calculate the input stresses could provide additional insights on the material behaviour.

FIGURE 1 Basis of the model used by Noroozi et al. to predict crack tip stresses (from [1])

DISCUSSION

Finite element modelling method

The model used for the finite element analyses is shown in Figure 2. A 1.4mm long notch with a $10\mu\text{m}$ end radius is contained within a rectangular section 7mm wide and 30mm long. The crack length and section geometry were chosen to match an experimental condition where an amplitude change was introduced to the loading cycle. Advantage was taken of the geometry's symmetry to model only the top half of the crack and surrounding material. 4-noded CPS4 elements were used with linear geometry.

The model also contains a row of fully rigid elements shown in brown which runs from the crack mouth to just short of the run-out of the notch radius. The tops of these elements contact the crack face in such a way that they separate under tension but can transmit compressive stresses in the loading (y) direction if the crack is predicted to close. All the nodes on the bottom edge of the cracked geometry and contact block are fixed in the y direction, and the nodes at the notch root and the bottom right-hand corner of the contact block are also pinned in the x direction.

A uniform pressure load is applied to the top of the model, and the nodal displacements there in the loading direction are all set to be equal using the ABAQUS *EQUATION keyword. This is not strictly necessary, but represents the remote boundary conditions for a threaded test piece more appropriately than allowing the nodes there to deform freely.

The geometry was generated using a macro in Microsoft Excel, and a variety of node/element patterns close to the notch root have been used over the course of the overall research programme. The version used for this study contains multiple layers of elements ahead of the crack tip $0.25\mu\text{m}$

wide that, in other work, have been switched off progressively as the load was cycled to simulate crack growth whilst maintaining the original crack tip radius. Finally, five rings of elements around the arc of the notch root were specified by the *CONTOUR INTEGRAL keyword to allow J-integral values to be calculated as part of the analyses.

FIGURE 2 Edge crack 2D plane stress finite element model - mesh geometry and loading details

Example stress contours in the loading direction from elastic and plastic analyses are shown in Figure 3. Initial analyses had kinks in the contours around the shallow angled elements at the top of the notch radius which were largely resolved by splitting each of them horizontally into five smaller elements. This detail can be seen in the magnified region of Figure 2.

FIGURE 3 Loading direction stress contours from elastic and plastic FE analyses, FG RR1000 at 20°C, $K_{max}=25.8\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$

The suitability of the sharp notch for representing the crack tip stress field was then established. Geometry correction factors Y for nine different crack lengths were calculated from the ABAQUS J-integral output for models run with no constraints on the top edge. These were then compared with the standard solution for edge cracks developed by Brown and Srawley [7] as shown in Figure 4.

The FE results are within 0.5% of the Brown and Srawley values throughout. Also shown in Figure 4 are the effects of constraining the top of the model to remain horizontal as it deforms, which are significant for longer edge cracks. The addition of this boundary condition is equivalent to superposing a compressive load to the top of the model above the cracked region, reducing the elastic stresses and hence the Y and K values.

Additional sensitivity calculations exploring a 1µm notch radius, non-linear geometry and different values of Young’s modulus and Poisson’s ratio all gave Y values within 0.7% of the datum FE results. The elastic stress-distance profile close to the notch root in the crack growth direction was also checked to confirm that it captured the expected 1/√r singularity well.

Having determined that the modelling method was appropriate to represent the crack tip stress fields, plastic R=0 FE analyses were run at nineteen different peak loads representing a K range from 1-86MPa√m. Isotropic plasticity was used with a single cycle zero-max-zero loading history. The plasticity data for FG RR1000 at 20°C was expressed in true stress-log strain form and was supplied by Rolls-Royce plc. Isotropic rather than kinematically hardened plasticity was used because the material close to the crack tip experiences higher absolute strain levels than it has seen previously with each load reversal and data from complex cycle strain controlled tests has shown that this causes its plastic response to follow an isotropic, rather than kinematically hardened, stress-strain curve.

FIGURE 4 Comparison of geometry correction factors from the FE model with those from the Brown and Srawley equation

Calculation of fatigue damage ahead of the moving crack tip stress field

Figure 5 shows the general principle behind representing crack growth as progressive material failure due to the accumulation of damage from successive fatigue loading cycles as the crack tip moves towards a point in the crack path. Initially the crack tip is at position A, and the maximum and minimum stress-distance profiles associated with the loading cycle extremes are shown by the dark green lines. At a location C some distance ahead of the crack tip the fatigue loading cycle will be relatively modest. As the crack grows and the tip reaches B, however, the stress range experienced at location C increases, reaching a maximum value when the crack tip approaches that point.

FIGURE 5 Increasing maximum and minimum stress fields experienced at a location as the crack tip moves towards it

The plastic maximum and minimum stress fields for a specific loading cycle were moved towards the location where the fatigue damage is calculated in $1\mu\text{m}$ steps in an Excel spreadsheet, starting with the notch root $300\mu\text{m}$ away. At each step, the fatigue damage in N loading cycles ($=N/N_f$ where N_f is the number of cycles to failure) is calculated using a Basquin-style [8] life equation based on the Walker [9] corrected equivalent 0-max stress at the current distance from the crack tip as shown in equations (1) and (2). A threshold stress below which no damage occurs is also included in the life equation. The fatigue damage values from each step are summed, and the value of N is then calculated such that the total fatigue damage at the calculation location is equal to unity when the crack tip reaches it. The crack growth rate for this geometry and loading condition is then the size of the crack tip movement step ($1\mu\text{m}$) divided by N .

$$\frac{(\Delta\sigma_{equiv\ 0-max} - \sigma_{th})}{UTS} = \alpha \cdot (N_f)^\beta \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta\sigma_{equiv\ 0-max} = \Delta\sigma(1 - R)^{(m-1)} \quad (2)$$

In equations (1) and (2) σ_{th} is the threshold value of equivalent 0-max stress, UTS is the material's Ultimate Tensile Strength, α and β are fitting parameters and m is the Walker exponent.

The S-N (stress-life) curve used to calculate the fatigue damage ahead of the crack tip was fitted to FG RR1000 LCF test results from plain specimens run under strain and load control at two different loading R-ratios. Unfortunately, no results were available at 20°C and therefore data from 300°C tests were used instead. The fatigue lives at this temperature are expected to be similar to but slightly lower than those at 20°C for equivalent loading conditions. The load controlled test lives are to failure, and the strain controlled lives are to a 10% load drop relative to stabilised stress conditions. Two different surface conditions were used for the fatigue tests, polished and shot peened, although the lives were similar and therefore the data were combined.

The strain controlled tests were analysed using a single element FE model through one loading cycle with isotropic plasticity and 20°C material properties to calculate maximum and minimum stresses. This is consistent with the calculation method used to determine the maximum and minimum crack tip stress fields and helps to scale the test results across to the temperature that will be used for the crack growth rate predictions.

The fitted values of the parameters m , σ_{th}/UTS , α and β were 0.44, 0.31, 3.60 and -0.17. This gives the curve shown on the left-hand side of Figure 6, which collapses the test data well for all the different loading conditions. Because the relationship between equivalent 0-max plastic stress and peak elastic stress is different for the two R-ratios, equations (1) and (2) generate separate curves on peak elastic stress-life axes as shown on the right of Figure 6. The full curve shapes shown in this plot were predicted by running additional single element plastic FE simulations at a wide range of R=0 and R=-1 strain controlled loading conditions.

FIGURE 6 Fitted fatigue curves based on plastic stresses, fine grain RR1000 material at 300°C

The initial $da/dN-\Delta K$ curve prediction depended solely on the stress fields ahead of the crack tip from the plastic FE analyses and the fit to the plain test piece LCF data. When the crack tip is close to the calculation position, however, the stresses are very high and the corresponding fatigue damage rate comes from extrapolating the curves in Figure 6 to low lives. It is possible for this extrapolation to be varied slightly without upsetting the fit to the test data, and therefore an improved fitting method was developed that had inputs of both the LCF data and typical crack growth design data for fine grain RR1000 at 20°C. This fitting method also makes the growth rate predictions largely independent of the notch radius used in the FE models because the position of the fatigue S-N curve at very high stresses automatically adjusts to give similar growth rate curves. The curves shown in Figure 6 use this method.

The resulting predicted crack growth rate curve for R=0 is compared with typical design data and test results from the current programme in Figure 7. The curve exhibits threshold-like behaviour at low K values and the slope also increases at high K values due to the FE model experiencing plastic strain across the whole ligament of material ahead of the crack. In the ΔK range of 15-40MPa $\sqrt{m}$, where most experimental data are usually collected, the growth rate- ΔK relationship is approximately linear and its slope is very close to the database value. Overall the agreement with the test data and the design data are extremely good, although the predicted threshold ΔK value is a little low compared to the typical value from tests of around 8MPa $\sqrt{m}$.

FIGURE 7 Comparison of predicted crack growth rates from the fatigue analogy method with database Paris law values and experimental data, FG RR1000 at 20°C

Growth rate predictions for other R-ratios

The effects of loading R-ratio on crack growth rates were then studied by running two further series of 2D plane stress analyses at R=-1 and R=0.5. As shown in Figure 8(a), close to the crack tip the plastic equivalent 0-max stress-distance profiles for the same peak applied load at R=0 and R=-1 are very similar and therefore the predicted growth rates for R=-1 were only slightly faster despite the applied load range being twice that at R=0 conditions. This trend was consistent across the range of applied loads and lined up exactly with the behaviour seen in tests conducted by Rolls-Royce.

FIGURE 8 Comparison of equivalent 0-max stress-distance profiles ahead of the crack tip from (a) R=0 and R=-1 loading profiles and (b) R=0 and R=0.5 loading profiles at different K_{max} values

The trends are different, however, between $R=0.5$ and $R=0$ as shown in Figure 8(b). The $R=0$ equivalent stress-distance profiles are significantly higher those for $R=0.5$ at low K_{max} values. As K_{max} increases the profiles then start to coalesce at the crack tip location and the predicted fatigue damages and hence crack growth rates become more similar. This can be seen in the left-hand plot of Figure 9. The interesting thing about this figure is that it clearly shows that whilst the $da/dN-\Delta K$ curves are parallel for $R=0$ and $R=-1$, the predicted $R=0.5$ curve is steeper. Data available in the literature (Dinda [10], Zheng [11], Bulloch [12] and Huang [13]) goes against this prediction, however, and often suggests that the $R=0.5$ crack growth curves are flatter than for $R=0$. Clear trends can be difficult to establish, however, because of high scatter in the measured crack growth rates. Laboratory tests will therefore be performed to generate $R=0.5$ data for FG RR1000.

FIGURE 9 Predicted $R=0$, -1 and 0.5 crack growth curves for FG RR1000 material at 20°C based on stress-distance profiles from 2D plane stress analyses and plain test piece LCF data

Overload behaviour

Finally, the expected growth rates following a reduction in applied load were predicted using the fatigue analogy. This is a much more complex calculation, and was implemented in Excel using a Visual Basic macro rather than formulae in specific worksheet cells. This greatly reduced the physical size of the spreadsheet and allowed a finer user-defined spatial resolution of as small as $0.1\mu\text{m}$ per calculation step to be used. It also allowed the K values and stress fields to be modified as the crack moves and grows. The main inputs to the macro were plastic maximum and minimum stress-distance profiles for a wide range of K_{max} values and the peak applied load as a function of crack length.

Two loading conditions will be discussed. Both are at $R=0$ and reduce the amplitude of the peak load when the crack length is 1.4mm , either to 80% or 40% of its initial value. To allow the fatigue damage some time to build up ahead of the crack tip, the calculations were started at a crack length of 1.3mm . The fatigue damage was determined at a large number of locations separated from each other by the calculation step length over a distance of 1mm from the starting position i.e. from $1.3\text{--}2.3\text{mm}$ ahead of the crack mouth in these examples.

The calculation process for the spreadsheet macro is shown in Figure 10. Based on the K value calculated for the starting crack length and peak load using edge geometry correction factor polynomials for constrained conditions, initial plastic stress-distance profiles are determined by interpolation between the closest sets of FE results. Increments of fatigue damage are then calculated

at all the locations in the 1mm calculation length. The crack tip position is then moved progressively through the material and the above calculation process is repeated, with the fatigue damage increments at each location ahead of the crack tip being summed, until the reduced pressure load and corresponding crack length for the load drop are found in the input data. At this time, the fatigue damage calculated during all the previous timesteps and at all locations within the material is scaled by the same factor such that the value at the current crack tip position is unity. This allows the $da/dN-\Delta K$ behaviour to date to be output.

FIGURE 10 Excel macro flowchart for calculating overload behaviour using the fatigue analogy for crack growth

To describe the subsequent crack growth, a number of assumptions first have to be made about how the minimum (residual) stress field established just before the load reduction combines with the moving stress fields from the subsequent lower amplitude cycle:

- The residual compressive stress field resulting from the overload is assumed to remain fixed in space and to remain constant as the crack grows because contact between the crack faces maintains a consistent load-carrying area for these compressive stresses
- When the crack tip has moved to a distance x ahead of its initial position, the peak tensile stress in the cycle at that location is given by the overload residual stress at x plus the crack tip stress range corresponding to the K value for the new crack length and reduced load range
- As the crack grows further, it will reach a position where the overload residual stress field at x is less compressive than the minimum crack tip stress field associated with $R=0$ loading at the current K range. The minimum crack tip stress is then assumed to be that from the $R=0$ analysis. This is because the maximum and minimum crack tip stress fields are assumed to equilibriate at this level: additional yielding at one extreme of the loading cycle would generate higher stresses in the opposite direction at the other end of the loading cycle which would return the stresses to their starting values
- Ahead of the crack tip, the minimum stress is assumed to be the lower of that from the residual stress field and the $R=0$ analysis at the current K range

- The maximum stress field is determined by adding the stress range-distance profile for the current K value to the minimum stress field

The implementation of these assumptions was checked in detail by comparing stress-distance profiles produced by the spreadsheet against the behaviour from an analysis where, after a load drop, bands of elements ahead of the crack tip were removed progressively to grow the crack and evolve the stress fields.

As described previously, at the crack length where the load drop occurs all of the calculated fatigue damages are scaled by the same factor such that the value at the crack tip is unity. The fatigue damage at the next location ahead of the crack tip will then be close to this value. The crack tip is moved to that point, and using the above assumptions first the minimum and then the maximum stress field are determined by combining the contributions from residuals and the current loading. The fatigue damage per cycle is calculated everywhere, and based on the difference between unity and the previous damage at the crack tip location the number of cycles required to cause this material to fail is calculated. The current damage rate is multiplied by this cycle number and added to the previous fatigue damage values at all the other locations ahead of the crack tip. This calculation process is repeated to grow the crack, with the number of cycles required to fail the current ligament of material always varying because of the changing stress fields and different amounts of prior fatigue damage. Crack growth rates throughout this process are defined as the calculation step length divided by the number of cycles to fail each successive ligament.

Predictions of the initial crack growth rates at the higher load and the behaviour after the two levels of load reduction are shown in Figure 11. Because the calculations begin with zero damage, it takes a number of increments of crack tip movement and fatigue damage accumulation before the process stabilises and growth rates similar to the design data are generated. This behaviour is shown by the blue curve in Figure 11.

For both the load reduction simulations the growth rates return to the levels that would be predicted without a load drop when the extremes of the plastic zones from the currently applied load and the previous higher load are coincident. This is expected behaviour, and results from the assumptions made to generate the stress fields following the load drop. The calculations, however, show marked oscillations in the predicted crack growth rates. This is particularly evident in the case of the drop to 80% of the previous maximum load, and is considered to be an artefact of using finite width calculation steps and the presence of fluctuations and sometimes sub-surface peaks in the stress fields when the residuals from the overload are included. These stress field fluctuations mean that sometimes the next calculation point has accumulated almost as much fatigue damage as at the current crack tip location. Very few cycles are then required to cause failure there, resulting in a high crack growth rate. The damage one step ahead of the new crack tip position will only have increased by a small amount during this step, however, and it may then require a higher number of additional cycles before it becomes unity. This results in a slow predicted crack growth rate in this increment and the behaviour persists, resulting in the oscillations seen in the predicted growth rate.

The oscillations are still present in the growth rate predictions for the drop to 40% of the previous maximum load, but these are smaller because the stress fields in this scenario are much smoother. The growth rates from the fatigue predictions do not reduce to their minimum value immediately after the load drop, but instead decrease sharply over a short distance because of prior fatigue damage ahead of the crack tip from the previous higher amplitude loading. This phenomenon has been seen in testing by a number of authors including Antunes, Castanheira and Branco [14]. The overall shape of the green curve in Figure 11 curve also looks to be an improvement over that predicted by the

approaches developed by Wheeler [15] and Willenborg [16], which approach the ‘conventional’ crack growth curve abruptly rather than tangentially as shown here. Further development of the fatigue-based method for load drops and overloads is therefore warranted.

FIGURE 11 Overload crack growth rate predictions made based on fatigue behaviour: 1.4mm edge crack in 7mm wide section, cycle K values of 0-32.3MPa√m followed by either 0-25.8MPa√m or 0-12.9MPa√m, fine grain RR1000 material at 20°C

CONCLUSIONS

The finite element analysis style used has been shown to reproduce established geometry correction factors for edge cracks (and, in other work by Williams [17], for 3D corner cracks) very closely.

It has also been shown that a curve fit performed to fatigue test results on plain smooth specimens can be used to generate low temperature crack growth rates that agree extremely well with database values. Further work is needed, however, to improve the threshold ΔK prediction. Current ideas for this include averaging the calculated stresses over some length scale, potentially the grain size of the material, based on the idea that the material cannot easily react to large stress gradients over a length scale smaller than a grain.

Use of the calculation method for other loading R-ratios has provided an analytical basis for the similarity in growth rates observed in R=0 and R=-1 loading cycles for the same peak load. The prediction of an increased da/dN - ΔK curve slope at R=0.5 was unexpected and will be explored further.

A revised damage accumulation method is also required to allow post-overload behaviour to be predicted without exhibiting oscillations in the crack growth rate. There will still be the issue, however, that the lower crack growth rates generated by load reductions and overloads persist to significantly greater crack lengths in corner cracked specimen tests than expected from standard theory and the fatigue-based model predictions.

LIST OF SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATIONS

a	Crack length
α	Lifing curve parameter related to its intercept
β	Lifing curve parameter related to its slope
K	Stress intensity factor
m	Walker exponent
N	Number of applied fatigue cycles
N_f	Number of fatigue cycles to failure
r	Distance ahead of the crack tip
ρ^*	Notch root radius and calculation block size in the Noroozi model
σ_{th}	Threshold stress value in fatigue curve equation
Y	Geometry correction factor in stress intensity formula

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The academic authors are grateful for the financial support provided for this work by Rolls-Royce plc. The work was carried out at the Institute of Structural Materials in Swansea University as part of a Ph.D. project.